

Repository Profile:

REPOSITAN.

The Open Access Repository:

Citizen view of the research in Andalucía, Spain

SICA2 is the second generation of the curricula database of all researchers in Andalusia, Spain. It comprises the all the activity and scientific production of the researchers of ten public Universities, Research and Health Institutions. Private and non Andalusian research institutions are also included.

SICA, began in 2002, is an institutional Competence Research Information System (CRIS), where it was conceived to provide deep assessment of the actual state of a very large research system. SICA2, the second version of SICA, launched in 2011, provides information about the multiple research activities done by the Andalusian researchers. It includes the Open Access Repository as part of the system, called REPOSITAN.

The objective is to find and share the knowledge and researchers, if they exist in Andalusia.

SICA in facts

Regional scope

15,580	Entities
709,636	Scientific activities
53,143	Researchers/Users
3,058	Research groups
10	Public Universities
1,608	Private associates

REPOSITAN

<http://sica2.cica.es/repositan>

Launched in October 2011

Platform: Alfresco

It currently hosts 1.133.086 publications from 53.000 authors of the Andalusian Knowledge System of Andalusia.

Digital resources are meta-documented from profiles of the authors with a complete context of the the scientific activity related with the publications, all stored in the CRIS platform SICA.

REPOSITAN is the official name of the institutional Open Access Repository for the Region of Andalusia. It is a response to the statement of the „Andalusian Science Law“ (LCA 16/2007, Dic 3rd) and the „Spanish Science Law“ (LCE 14/2011, June 1st). REPOSITAN is fed by the research results and publications, it stores a researcher’s production item while it is linked to a CRIS, called SICA. This way the curricula of all Adalusian Reseachers are enriched, regardless their scientific field and institution.

The purpose of REPOSITAN are:

- Dissemination as open access manner the scientific achievements to the citizens
- Store all the generated knowledge in a digital format.
- Be a visibility mean of the reseach results of scientific activities in Andalusia.
- Create a space to share knowledge and connect the researchers of a common or different fields

REPOSITAN offers a set of services:

- Metada extraction
- Advanced searching
- Federation with other institutional repositories following the DRIVER directives.

COAR Repository Observatory

<https://www.coar-repositories.org/activities/repository-observatory/>

Repository Profile:

REPOSITAN.

The Open Access Repository:

Citizen view of the research in Andalucía, Spain

from CRIS to REPOSITORY

REPOSITAN linked Open Data Initiative from INVESTIGAN to REPOSITAN

REPOSITAN is an initiative for the “Junta de Andalucía” government to promote the visibility and impact of the Andalusian scientific activities.

REPOSITAN is a proposal to be a central resource for the management of the research in Andalusia with the aim to improve the cohesion and visibility of the knowledge generated by our scientific community.

REPOSITAN interoperates with other repositories following the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) and the OAI-PMH protocol for harvesting.

REPOSITAN is an independent repository and, at the same time, it is connected with SICA2, the CRIS of the “Junta de Andalucía” regional government.

SICA2 provides to REPOSITAN the publication and resources generated by the scientific community of Andalusia and a set of metadata about the context of those resources.

Once a resource is added in SICA2, automatically the source is stored in REPOSITAN with its set of metadata obtained of the new curricular item and its author/group.

Key features of REPOSITAN

1. Enrichment of digital resources with superior metadata to Dublin Core specifications. It includes curricular and research data from the CRIS SICA2.
2. Digital Objects include metadata related
3. with research institutions and business regional network
4. Digital Objects include data about researchers, research groups and institutions
5. It manages public statistics to measure the impact of the research results, related with research group and institutions
6. It offers harvesting and enrichment services of data from third repositories
7. REPOSITAN is integrated with portals and search services of international institutions
8. Multilingual platforms

About CEICE - Junta de Andalucía

Andalucía is a region of Spain located in the south of the Iberian peninsula. CEICE is the regional ministry that funds research, development and innovation projects within the whole region. Andalucía is a convergence region with a population of about 8 million people. CEICE defines the regional strategy of research and innovation in Andalucía for public institutions. CEICE promoted and maintains the SICA2 as a strategic project. It has also promoted policies related to open access for data, resources and software in the last years.

[Website](#)

<http://sica2.cica.es>

sica2@cica.es

What's next for REPOSITAN?

- Integration with researcher identifiers such as ORCID, ResearchID and SCOPUS in a bidirectional way.
- Introduce the DOI to identify the digital resources.
- Implement new metadata formats such as CERIF, METS, MARC for a better access to European funding calls.
- Exploit the database contents, as a high quality information system and work as a facility, open to the community, to study many aspects of research in Andalusia.

COAR Repository Observatory

<https://www.coar-repositories.org/activities/repository-observatory/>